

ABOUT THE DIALECTOLOGICAL SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of dialect concepts in a comparative plan and the path of development of future teachers in the professional sphere. In long-distance areas dialects, dialect systems and folklore still exist. Improving the system of comparative dialect competence of the Russian and Uzbek languages at present can give a methodical direction to students of the national group. A competent approach to the study of the dialect system develops the knowledge of future Russian language teachers in national schools. Dialect words in both the Uzbek language and the Russian language are considered in a semantic aspect.

Key words: dialect words, semantics, comparative dialectological competence.

INTRODUCTION

“For many years I wandered around the cities, villages and pastures of Turks, Turkmens, Oguzes, Chigils, Yagmas and Kyrgyz, collected the most exquisite words and expressions, studied and established various lexical features. I did this not because I do not know the language, but in order to determine the slightest differences between these languages ”

Mahmud Kashgariy

Philologist and philosopher of the nineteenth century V. Humboldt said: "... language is the combined spiritual energy of the people, miraculously captured in certain sounds, in this guise and through the interconnection of their sounds, understandable to all speakers and excite about the same energy in them ...". In order to preserve the purity of the national language, the languages of folk traditions in the territory of our native land, it is very important to understand the thoughts of our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “..... you should deeply study the features of the Uzbek language and its dialects, issues related to its history and development prospects, increase the effectiveness of specialized scientific research, dramatically improve the quality of training”.

THE MAIN PART

Dialect vocabulary is a system which has a dialect word as a main unit .

F.P. Filin defines a dialect word as "a word that has a local distribution and at the same time is not included in the vocabulary of the literary language (in any of its varieties)."

“The beginning of the nineteenth century in Russia is characterized by a revival of socio-political life, the rise of national identity, especially after the war of 1812. It is then that interest arises in the comprehensive study of the peasantry: its customs, beliefs, culture,

language, ethnography develops (from the Greek ethnos - “people”), which studies the material and spiritual culture of the people. It is then that interest arises in the comprehensive study of the peasantry: its customs, beliefs, culture, language, ethnography develops (from the Greek ethnos - “people”), which studies the material and spiritual culture of the people. Researchers recorded mostly “exotic” words and phrases related to the description of local customs and rituals. So, with the collection of local words and vivid expressions, the science of dialectology began (from the Greek dialektos - “conversation, dialect, adverb” and logos - “word, doctrine”), studying local dialects, dialects” [2].

Dialectology of the Uzbek language - the study of the dialectic picture of the modern Uzbek language. The modern Uzbek language is characterized by a significant dialect branching, which is due to the complex ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people. Many ethnic groups took part in the ethnogenetic processes of the Central Asian interfluvium, among which were speakers of both East Iranian languages and Oguz, Karluk, and Kipchak dialects. Due to the close proximity and the closest ethno-cultural contacts, the Uzbek language has been influenced by the significant influence of the Tajik language.

In turn, the Uzbek language had a huge impact both on the Tajik language and on the Turkic languages of the region.

In general, in the process of improving this system, as mentioned above, in a comparative aspect, within the functioning of the Russian and Uzbek languages, one can keep in mind such features as each language has its own national mentality and individual sides in folklore.

A competent approach to improving the comparative dialectological system has an important place in integrating the education of future teachers of the Russian language.

A focus on competency-based education is already being formed in the 70s. XX century in America in the context of the concept of “competency” proposed by N. Chomsky as applied to transformational grammar [9, 240 p.]. Chomsky writes: “... we draw a fundamental distinction between competence (speaking and listening to one’s own language) and use (real use of the language in specific situations). Only in an idealized case ... use is a direct reflection of competence” [10, p. 9]. We draw attention to the fact that “use”, according to Chomsky, is a manifestation of competence as something potential, that is, use is associated with skills, thinking, the speaker himself, his experience [9, 240 p.].

Competencies are interpreted as a single (coherent) language for describing academic and professional profiles and levels of higher education. It is sometimes said that the language of competencies is the most appropriate for describing the results of education. Orientation of standards, curricula (educational programs) to the results of education makes qualifications comparable and transparent, which cannot be said about the content of education, which is strikingly different not only between countries but also universities, even when preparing for the same specialty (subject area) . So far, no more modern methodological tool for the Bologna update has been found in European universities. According to Western experts, the results of education expressed in the language of competencies are a way to expand academic and professional recognition and mobility, to increase the comparability and compatibility of diplomas and qualifications. In Russia, the implementation of the competency-based approach can be an additional factor in maintaining a single educational, vocational-qualification and cultural-value space [1, p. 6.]

General and professional competencies form a kind of **complementary** unity. General (key, universal) competencies, according to prof. Yu. Kohler, should be a pedagogically appropriate tool to increase the ability to find employment and actually didactic quality [3].

Creating a dialectological atlas can show the distinguishing features of two languages.

There is no need at this point to dwell on how important the creation of such an atlas will be, not only for clarifying the distinguishing features of modern dialects, but also for the comparative historical grammar of the Turkic languages, for their genetic classification, for the history of the Turkic-speaking peoples, creators and carriers of these languages. Here I would only like to touch on some general methodological and methodological problems of compiling the atlas, arising from the experience of national and regional dialectological atlases, which currently exist in a fairly large number both abroad and in our country [4, p. 55].

When we start collecting material for a dialectological atlas, we are not entitled to proceed from the widespread presumption that modern dialects of Turkic languages represent closed "branches", "limbs" and "sprigs" of the family tree, branching out by sequential differentiation from the "common Turkic" trunk according to a straight line decay pattern in dialects - dialects and subdialects of local dialects. Linguistic geography does not come from closed, spontaneously developed dialect massifs, outlined by a set of distinguishing features; it is based on establishing and considering how the boundaries of the individual and the future are [4, p.55].

The study of Uzbek dialects using the methods of linguogeography began in 1944, when A. K. Borovkov compiled a questionnaire "Questions on the study of Uzbek dialects". With the help of this questionnaire, he spent 1945-1950 years collecting materials on dialects of the Ferghana Valley. However, the absence at that time of a unified dialectological scientific center did not allow the development of materials and a map. After that, the question was removed from the agenda, and research was resumed only 20 years later, in 1965 [5, 16-17].

Mapping of Uzbek dialects was started by V.V. Reshetov. For many years he studied the dialects of the Tashkent region, in particular, the dialect group of the Akhangaran Valley. For the first time in Uzbek dialectology, 49 linguistic maps of Kuramin dialects were compiled [6].

At the end of the 70s of the XX century, the dialectological maps of Khorezm (F. A. Abdullaev), Bukhara (M. Mirzaev), Namangan (A. Aliyev), Kashkadarya (A. Shermatov) were completed. In 1980, the "Atlas of dialects of the Tashkent region" was published, consisting of 150 maps [7, p. 18]. Works on mapping Uzbek dialects of Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Andijan and other regions were suspended in the 90s. XX century.

I. I. Sreznevsky was the first scientist who in 1852 raised the question of creating a map on which the boundaries of languages, dialects and dialects of the Russian language would be indicated. At this time, **V. I. Dahl** was engaged in the study of dialect vocabulary, who was interested in the dialects of the Russian language in terms of their origin and classification. A.I. Sobolevsky in 1892 for the first time introduced the teaching of Russian dialectology as an independent discipline at universities, giving a course of lectures on it. And already in 1897 a separate textbook appeared, entitled "Experience of Russian dialectology." In it, on the basis of the collected materials, Sobolevsky tried to identify the main units of dialect division, to determine the territory of these units and to name their characteristic features. Sobolevsky introduced into scientific use all the material collected from the dialects of the Russian

language.

CONCLUSION

The question of creating a dialectological atlas was posed at the N. Ya. Marr Institute of Language and Thinking at the Academy of Sciences in 1935. A group of scientists was created that needed to work on this atlas (B.A. Larin, F.F. Filin and etc.), a “Data Gathering Program for the Dialectological Atlas of the Russian Language” was developed. Method - direct observation of linguists who need to be specially trained. A transcription was developed, localities were identified in which it was proposed to collect material (the original Russian population must have lived in them) [8].

It can be said that the dialectological map of the comparative system provides such information that can be developed by future teachers of the Russian language integration knowledge.

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